

RM ROADMAP

Deliverable 6.2 Sustainability Report

This deliverable provides conclusions of Sustainability Report for the RM Communities and Stakeholders. This report is prepared in month 36 of the project (August 2025) and is due as Deliverable 6.2.

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D6.2: Sustainability Report

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RM Roadmap_ASTP WP6 D6.2 Sustainability Report

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RM Roadmap_ASTP WP6 D6.2 Sustainability Report

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Contents

1.	Introduction RM Roadmap.....	5
2.	Summary	5
3.	Background for the Sustainability Report.....	6
4.	Clear Goals of Sustainability Planning	7
5.	RM Landscape Evolution: Terminology Framework	7
6.	RM Landscape Evolution: Harnessing a Mature RM Landscape	8
7.	Connectivity of Networks	9
8.	Review of the Commercial Potential of RM Roadmap Outputs as the basis of Sustainability (e.g. Platforms for the RM Communities).....	10
9.	Synergies with other Initiatives	11
10.	Key Conclusions of the Sustainability Report	12
11.	Sustainability Recommendations to be further reinforced in the final RM Roadmap.....	13
	Figure 1: Graphic representation of the Overarching Roadmap	14

List of Abbreviations

ATTP	Association of Technology Transfer Professionals
COARA	Coalition for Advancing Research Management
D	Deliverable
EARMA	European Association of Research Managers and Administrators
ERA	European Research Area
EUSA	European School of Administration
KCP	Knowledge and Community Platform
LES	Licensing Executive Society
RM	Research Management
R&D	Research and Development
R&I	Research and Innovation

RM Roadmap_ASTP WP6 D6.2 Sustainability Report

1. Introduction RM Roadmap

RM Roadmap has charted a course for the future of research management (RM) in Europe and a community to support its delivery.

The overarching objective of RM Roadmap is to identify and promote ways to adapt the research management capital base of the EU, including the widening countries, with a focus to identify the emerging needs of its current and future research management workforce to improve the EU's competitiveness and ability to sustain its economic performance and growth.

RM Roadmap facilitated the many existing European networks of research and innovation managers to connect on a smart community platform which enabled an unprecedented consultation process towards understanding key issues affecting research management. This co-creation process gathered the existing communities together and expanded upon them to reach two main objectives: to create and inform a bottom-up consensus on the future of RM in a roadmap, and to inform the community about existing training, networking, funding, and career mobility opportunities.

Eight partners worked together on this project: European Association of Research Managers and Administrators (Belgium); HETFA Research Institute (Hungary); Nova University Lisbon (Portugal); Association of European Science & Technology Transfer Professionals (Netherlands); Crowdhelix Limited (Ireland), The Cyprus Institute (Cyprus) and associated partners Janssen Pharmaceuticals (J&J) and Una Europa (Belgium).

2. Summary

Since the RM Roadmap project has a finite lifespan, one of the key deliverables under WP6 Sustainability and Exploitation is to develop a strategy to ensure sustainability of the vision and outputs of the project. Not only the vision but its tangible outputs are expected to have the possibility to continue under a variety of different routes. Planning for such longevity and potential impact was a process started early in the project with a Sustainability Plan being delivered as D6.1 Sustainability Plan.

Building on the Plan, this more expanded Sustainability Report describes the specific tangible actions and processes developed and enshrines recommendations regarding the longer sustainability of some of the achievements of the project. These will be seen to be based on the deliverables achieved and wider output achieved during the project. One additional feature of this Sustainability Report is that the recommendations can also harness several parallel developments from across the research and innovation landscape that were not anticipated as part of the planning of the original RM project.

To define the content of the Sustainability Report, we look to the RM Roadmap project and its overall objective to make the research and innovation (R&I) system in Europe become more efficient and more impactful, by delivering a Roadmap for the future of research management (RM) in the European Research Area (ERA)¹ by ensuring strategic strengthening of the RM community.

As described in the Sustainability Plan in M12, it was identified that the first likely pillars of sustainability would be around the evolution of the sophisticated, connected and visible RM landscape with key ingredients identified for such a landscape to become established are set out here.

The second main pillar was anticipated as being the structured access to platforms to enable not only operational exchanges of information during the project but also to remain as essential tools to enable ongoing visibility of tools and training capacities, strengthening of networks and further evolution of the RM community at both national

¹ ERA is the priority within the RM ROADMAP project. The ERA includes member states, countries associated to Horizon Europe, which are non-EU countries and have formal agreements to participate in the EU's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme.

RM Roadmap_ASTP WP6 D6.2 Sustainability Report and European levels.

In setting the scene for future activities by stakeholders, the project's final output will be the formal RM Roadmap. This Sustainability Report focuses on the specific tangible results in the nature of new platforms, tools and ways of connecting newly created and existing communities of research managers, as defined in the ERA. Furthermore, elements of the Sustainability Report will also feature in the final RM Roadmap with its detailed proposals and recommendations for implementation of the wider goals of ERA Action 17.

3. Background for the Sustainability Report

This Sustainability Report is required to help not only the consortium partners but all stakeholders in the RM community move the project outputs to a post-project phase where the continuity of the project goals can deliver outcomes beyond the project lifecycle. The early observations and anticipated sustainability areas of focus identified in D6.1 Sustainability Plan can be seen to have been fulfilled therefore the structure of this Report reflects several of these areas of achievement with foundations for continuity.

In addition, the other deliverables of the project have also contributed, as well as the meetings hosted in person and online, bringing together communities of networks of practitioners as well as wider stakeholders. For example, the in-person ambassador meetings in Budapest (2023), Lisbon (2024) and Brussels (2025), together with online stakeholder meetings hosted as part of WP3 in February and May 2025 were attended by representatives of a broad spectrum of regions and stakeholders. Experiences and opinions expressed in such meetings contributed widely not only to the content of the formal deliverables but also allowed strong interpersonal, cross-sectoral relationships to be developed which aid the momentum and desire for effective sustainability after the project, all towards achievement of the goals of ERA Action 17.

To produce this Sustainability Report, the results obtained in the project have been reviewed. These include the final and draft deliverables from WP2 Training and Development which identify sustainability recommendations to maintain the increased awareness amongst research management staff about existing training, networking and mobility opportunities at EU, national, and regional levels.

- D1.1. Preliminary Report on ERA-wide landscape (M12)
- D2.1. Preliminary Report on professional development opportunities (M12)
- D2.2. Online tool for professional development opportunities (M24)
- D2.3. Report on the professional development opportunities (M34)

From WP4 *Communication* it has been possible to ensure that identification of relevant stakeholders and seek to ensure their engagement experiences throughout the life of the RM Roadmap project:

- D4.2. Online Knowledge and Community Platform (KCP) M6
- D4.4 Preliminary Dissemination, Communication and Exploitation report M12
- D4.5. Activity Report on Knowledge and Community Platform M34
- D4.6. Dissemination, Communication and Exploitation report M34

From WP3 *Advocacy* it has been possible to identify that the key focus of the scope of sustainability routes reflect the ERA calls for support and practical measures around recognition, upskilling, networking and capacity-building for research management.

- D3.1. Short policy brief 1 (M12)

In addition to the contents of the RM Roadmap project itself, engagement with several stakeholders also driving forward the goals of ERA Action 17 has led to further developments which set the scene for ongoing advancement of several of the Project objectives, as will be seen later in this Report. This Sustainability Report has therefore identified several areas of key focus for the legacy of the RM Roadmap project. These are set out below in points

RM Roadmap_ASTP WP6 D6.2 Sustainability Report

5 through to 10 and for each focus area a brief description together with key recommendations are set out.

4. Clear Goals of Sustainability Planning

Given the clear goals of RM Roadmap, it became clear that future sustainability of the results of this project cannot be planned for along the lines of most other EU-funded projects where future activities traditionally included potential plans around commercial income generation models to sustain the existence and effective running of new tools or platforms. However, since the RM landscape in Europe already comprises many useful networks, tools and processes, the Sustainability Report provides recommendations on how these existing networks and platforms can continue to remain accessible, visible and available to all relevant stakeholders and professionals. Such ongoing access and visibility also ensure that new and/or reinforced networks, using new and existing tools, will also become embedded within the RM landscape.

The RM Roadmap Sustainability Plan therefore focuses on the following key areas of action:

- Stronger networks across the RM community to be further supported.
- Dedicated ongoing engagement with and by the wider stakeholders in a position to facilitate, drive and support the actions identified in the RM Roadmap.
- Both the networks and wider stakeholders should further develop and maintain links with the detailed actions identified below as already under way or created in parallel to this RM Roadmap project.
- All stakeholders shall use their influence as well as building on the inspirational examples of some Member States to encourage wider accession to ERA Action 17 by the remaining Member States.

A summary of the essential ingredients for each of these key pillars was originally identified in the Sustainability Plan. This Report is able to further update details of tangible outputs as well as to enhance the practical recommendations and aspirations of the wider community in the subsequent sections of this Report.

- RM Landscape evolution
 - Terminology Framework (Recognition)
 - Mature RM landscape (Recognition, Upskilling, Networking)
 - Connectivity of Networks: sustainable vision (Networking, Upskilling)
 - Empowering National and regional communities to support and grow strong RM
 - Utilization of the Value proposition for RM and its Impact

- Platform utilization

The Knowledge platforms constitute of two different systems. One for the co-creation (Knowledge and Community Platform and another for dissemination and impact acceleration (CrowdHelix RM Helix). There are multiple aspects to the platforms developed and hosted by CrowdHelix via the RM Helix and EARMA via the Knowledge and Community Platform which will act as an ongoing networking tool to drive thought leadership across multiple sectors of the RM ecosystem.

- The Knowledge and Community Platform is embedded within the existing EARMA website openly accessible.
- The RM Helix is existing and proven technology which will remain available to the research management community after the end of the project.

5. RM Landscape Evolution: Terminology Framework

Through the RM Roadmap survey and the second co-creation exercise, the terms "Research Manager," "Research Manager and Administrator," and "Research Management and Support Professional" were identified as most preferred terminologies by the community. For the time being, "Research Manager" shall be used as a collective/umbrella term at the EU level as it is also used in policy discussions. Its translation into national languages

RM Roadmap_ASTP WP6 D6.2 Sustainability Report

must be sensitive to national specificities. The Sustainability Report is pleased to recognize that progress for such a Framework was achieved not only building on the content of the deliverables of Work Packages 1, 2 and 3 (more fully listed above), the outcomes from the co-creation sessions as well as the RM Roadmap survey, but there was also significant progress as a result of two dedicated activities driven in parallel by the European Commission:

- In consultation with the ERA Action 17 Stakeholders Forum - a definition of Research Management was proposed in 2024.
- As a result of the elaboration of RM COMP together with [CARDEA](#)², a definition³ has been co-developed and proposed to enable pan-European development of embedded career structures to be developed at national levels.

6. RM Landscape Evolution: Harnessing a Mature RM Landscape

The key features of a mature RM landscape were foreseen in the deliverable WP3. Overarching Roadmap Plan. These aspects included harnessing the ingredients necessary for the establishment of successful professional ecosystems:

- **Recognition of RM professional careers:**
 - In January 2025, the *European Competence Framework for Research Managers (RM COMP)* was published by the European Commission, developed by CARDEA and RM Roadmap projects, in close consultation with the European Commission and relevant stakeholders. This framework provides a robust and actionable resource to support national-level assessment and institutional development efforts aimed at embedding and formally recognising essential research management roles. By offering a structured approach to professional competencies, RM COMP enables institutions to establish dedicated career pathways for research managers, aligned with, and complementary to, traditional academic career structures. The third co-creation exercise, which included feedback from the RM ambassador network, demonstrated strong community engagement and widespread awareness. This collective input reflects growing momentum toward the formal recognition of research management as a profession. To realise the full impact of RM Comp, it is now critical that policymakers and institutional leaders actively commit to implementing the framework within their respective domains. Their leadership will be key to driving sustainable change and ensuring that research management is embedded as a strategic function across the European Research Area.
 - One of the additional developments of the wider landscape alongside the accelerated [RM Competence Framework](#) has also been the launch of the EU- funded [RM Framework project](#) (Grant Agreement number 101188073) aims to support the development of an European qualification system for research management, enhancing interoperability and improving RM within the European Research Area (ERA). The Framework is designed to guide policy makers, training and networking providers in empowering individual research managers

² CARDEA is a Horizon Europe project, with an objective to enable the Professionalisation of Research Management as a valued career choice within the European Research Area. More information is available here: <https://www.ucc.ie/en/cardea/aboutus/>

³ Research Managers enable, facilitate and support the performance of research in all its applications. Research Managers hold generalist or specialised roles within the research and innovation ecosystem. Research Managers are based in all types of research performing organisations, including public and private universities, research institutes, research funding organizations, medical institutions, NGOs, companies, public authorities, and so on. We initiate an inclusive and flexible approach enabling the reflection on constantly emerging fields and job profiles when defining Research Management. Thus, Research Managers can work as research policy advisers, pre-award and post-award officers, project managers, impact managers, science communicators, financial managers and advisors, legal advisors, contract and compliance managers, data stewards, open science officers, research infrastructure managers and operators, equality, diversity and inclusion advisors, research ethics advisors, knowledge and technology transfer officers, innovation managers and business developers, knowledge brokers, human resource managers in research, AI experts, and leaders of research facilitation offices, etc.

RM Roadmap_ASTP WP6 D6.2 Sustainability Report

through standardised professional development programmes. By offering a common framework yet maintaining a flexible approach, the project acknowledges the local and national differences across Europe and aims to develop training that raises awareness, improves quality, and supports sustainable RM careers. This initiative involves stakeholders from ten countries (Belgium, Czechia, France, Germany, Hungary, Italy, Poland, Portugal, Romania and Spain), supported by an extensive network of European and national RM organisations. By engaging key stakeholders to develop modular, tailored solutions, including the creation of a quality label, the project aims to foster sustainable, long-term improvements in the professional development programmes for research managers across Europe. The project started on February 1, 2025, with a duration of 24 months and a budget of 1 million euro. This project is a further example of sustainability of the momentum being driven by practitioners (supported initially by EU funds) to ensure that practical implementation of the RM Competence Framework recognizes the practitioner realities. It is recommended that much can be done to ensure an effective dissemination and engagement strategy by the RM Framework project to ensure that the widest RM community is aware of its results and benefits from the models and best practices which will be gathered and generated.

- **Upskilling of RM professionals** will continue, building upon the raised awareness of the existence of training opportunities together with an enhanced capacity round motivation to share with access to training and upskilling tools building upon the following deliverables
 - D2.1. Preliminary Report on professional development opportunities (M12)
 - D2.2. Online tool for professional development opportunities (M24)
 - D2.3. Report on the professional development opportunities (M34)

Professional RM practitioners can continue to do much to further develop and promote access to effective upskilling by sharing best practices, encouraging the development and delivery of shared learning environments whether via formal training events or more indirect conference environments where professionals can exchange and also learn from the wider expert community. Within institutions and organizations, professional development and continued skills enhancement has long been recognized, but with the enhanced recognition of RM as a profession, commitment not only by employers but also by professionals to ensure continued development and access to upskilling opportunities is embedded. This approach is also recognized as being an effective way to ensure increased levels of recruitment and retention of staff skilled in the broad spectrum of Research Management roles.

- **Enhanced recognition and investment by institutional and policy leadership:** In addition to deliverable D1.1. Preliminary Report on ERA-wide landscape (M12) and D1.2 Final Report on ERA-Wide Landscape (M34, the value proposition supporting the rationale and benefits of a strong RM profession is contained in the Overarching Roadmap. These targeted resources remain available to institutional and policy leadership to support their additional development of measures required and inspire regional and national commitment to their respective RM ecosystems. At national level, reference to the different co-creation reports generated in the 3rd co-creation consultation will be useful to identify areas for added professional training investment, reflecting the range of roles undertaken in different regions.

7. Connectivity of Networks

One of the key strengths of this project has been the opportunity to identify and harness existing networks across the RM landscape. This enabled both a widening of access to existing networks as well as inspiring such networks to further expand and develop their activities, geographically as well as regards scope of activities. Examples of the

RM Roadmap_ASTP WP6 D6.2 Sustainability Report

activities and achievements of such new and enhanced networks created under the RM Roadmap project include the following:

- **Ambassador Network:** this network was created under this project and successfully engaged over 140 individuals across 40 countries, each acting as proactive links to their national communities, inspiring engagement in the co-creation exercises during the RM Roadmap project. However, as indicated in the testimonials of national ambassadors shared in the final in-person RM Roadmap Ambassadors meeting in Brussels in June 2025, this pan-European, cross-sectoral network of professionals has a strong ambition to retain an identity, connectivity and capacity to continue their exchanges at both national and pan-European level. This ambassador network looks to further inspire each other with examples of how the development of professional recognition, upskilling and engagement with wider stakeholders across the research and innovation landscape is proceeding at the national level. There is strong evidence therefore that such professional exchanges will continue on an informal basis and the EARMA-based KCP platform will continue to be available to the network. Additionally, emerging proposals towards the end of the RM Roadmap project are being gathered and further supported by EARMA to explore the range of ongoing visibility, communication and activity roles to be promoted by the continuation of an active RM Roadmap Ambassador network.
- **RM Online Community via [The Helix](#):** The RM Roadmap project delivered this newly dedicated platform designed for the purpose of disseminating project results and outcomes. **The RM Helix community hosts 1093 users and 369 organizations across 78 countries.** The expertise and strong position of Crowdhelix in the existing research and innovation landscape meant that not only was such a platform possible within the project but it also opened up access to the mainstream platform offered by Crowdhelix with its different helix sectors facilitating matchmaking and raising visibility of research and innovation opportunities across public and private sectors. However, given the demand which the RM ambassador network has generated at European and national level to maintain momentum around continued recognition and upskilling of the RM profession as the successful results of ERA Action 17 continue to move forward, Crowdhelix has committed to maintaining support for and access to its dedicated Research Management Helix on its portal for a further period of five years after the end of the RM Roadmap project.
- **Regional networks** alongside national networks and associations of professionals and other stakeholders have all been encouraged to collaborate during this RM Roadmap project. Examples include the Spanish landscape whereby they created a network of networks, bringing together research managers, institutional leadership and knowledge valorization partner networks across Spain under one community where cross-fertilization of knowledge and coordinated policies can be developed.

As well as the pan-European, cross-regional exchanges which can be facilitated with RM Helix and KCP. At national level much has been done to further the development of the national networks, both formal and informal. A guide to the development of such national networks has been worked up as part of the RM Roadmap and its publication will create an extremely useful reference to further encourage the establishment and growth of the national networks of research managers.

8. Review of the Commercial Potential of RM Roadmap Outputs as the basis of Sustainability (e.g. Platforms for the RM Communities)

In the Sustainability Plan, it was already clear that traditional commercial exploitation of results of outputs from the RM Roadmap Project were not to be considered likely. Given the subsequent developments and momentum across the whole RM landscape since the outline proposal objectives of the RM Roadmap were drafted, it has become clear that sustainability of these aims and objectives (which in turn derive their validity from the aims of

RM Roadmap_ASTP WP6 D6.2 Sustainability Report

ERA Action 17 aims) can be seen to be much more effectively implemented as a result of a combination of activities of all the stakeholders across the RM landscape. This does not only mean that financial investment is required, but rather that the impact of all the measures now in place requires a pre-emptive investment in motivation of all stakeholders to ensure the complex journey towards a stronger European research and innovation landscape supported and enhanced by a highly skilled, widely available community of professionals.

In brief, revisiting the original commercial potential of the technical platforms identified in the Sustainability Plan, the following update is presented.

- Commercial Exploitation Framework for the RM Roadmap platform

Given the development by Crowdhelix of an enhanced platform for the RM ecosystem within this project, the Sustainability Plan anticipated that there may be an opportunity to seek identification of the market structure, functionality of the new platform and accessibility conditions possibilities for after the end of the RM Roadmap project. However, it has also been agreed that for the foreseeable future, there is no commercial case for exploiting the RM Helix platform.

9. Synergies with other Initiatives

As RM Roadmap project has progressed, many other initiatives have been successful in producing policy papers, tools and other resources directly relevant to the goals of the RM Roadmap project. Those which are available to contribute to the ongoing sustainability of the outputs of RM Roadmap are identified here.

- **Policy outputs** from other ERA actions, such as research careers, research assessment and knowledge valorisation, and gender equality will contribute not only to the enhanced recognition of the RM profession but will contribute to the goals of enhancing recruitment and staff retention, all of which as necessary steps to provide for capacity building.
- RM Roadmap results will feed to the work on the new **Research Management action of the ERA Policy Agenda 2025-2027**. This upcoming initiative will launch in 2025 and flexile careers and competence framework for research managers. It will implement an evidence-based awareness campaign across Member States, with results expected in 2026, and co-create a European Charter for Research Managers through a cross-sectoral triangle approach involving research-performing organisations, funding bodies, and industry. The action will also design capacity-building strategies and analyse the role of research management in selected Horizon Europe “widening” actions to assess its impact on the efficiency and effectiveness of the R&I system. By 2027, a centralised online hub, ideally integrated into the ERA Talent Platform—will be launched to collate curricula, educational materials, upskilling tools, and access to training and certification programmes for current and aspiring research managers. These developments reflect the continued relevance and strategic value of the RM Roadmap’s outputs and community-driven momentum.
- **EU funded projects** which contribute to upskilling of RM professionals (training framework, proposal for quality label) will be developed by the RM Framework project which launched in February 2025. This project will develop tools which will enable assimilation and recognition of different training programs to aim for European-wide recognition approaches. Another synergy was between the RM Roadmap project and its sister project CARDEA. RM Roadmap conducted a mapping exercise (WP2), collecting 335 professional development opportunities in 39 European countries, which were feeding directly into the [CARDEA Dashboard](#) hosted by the CARDEA project. The dashboard serves as a comprehensive hub for RM professionals seeking professional development opportunities and was established in collaboration

RM Roadmap_ASTP WP6 D6.2 Sustainability Report

between the RM Roadmap project and the CARDEA project.

- **Networking and community developments:** EUSA/CoARA are examples of existing networks and initiatives which bring together key stakeholders at senior management level in institutions, encouraging the sharing of initiatives to promote enhancement of the ERA.
- **Stakeholder engagement:** dedicated briefing summaries will be produced as part of the Overarching Roadmap, and these materials will provide further insights into how the different stakeholder groups can promote the goals of embedding the RM profession across the ERA. However, as professionalization continues, across the broad spectrum of detailed skills and different roles, synergies with other professionalization bodies such as Association of Technology Transfer Professionals (ATTP), the Licensing Executive Society (LES) will continue to encourage the mutual recognition and establishment of accreditation schemes with pan-European impact.

10. Key Conclusions of the Sustainability Report

- **Ongoing Connectivity and Cross-fertilisation of activities:** The Sustainability Report takes account of the identified synergies with other projects and initiatives that not only were identified in the project application but all those subsequently gathered, in particular as part of the RM Roadmap Ambassador Network activities.
- **Identification of Roles for Different Stakeholders (policy/commercial/RM community):** Sustainability will ultimately depend upon ongoing engagement and commitment of all the RM stakeholders thus the RM Roadmap will further reinforce the ways in which be driven by the different stakeholders. Encouraging national policymakers as well as institutional leaders to drive acceptance and implementation of the RM profession.
- **Stronger Networks:** Aim to allow existing European networks to find ways to maintain existing national networks, to promote cross-regional exchanges by supporting access to and connections developed using the smart community platform. The co-creation process successfully gathered existing communities and expanded upon to create and inform a bottom-up consensus on the future of RM in the Overarching Roadmap. As well as providing insights to form the basis of roadmap recommendations for policy makers, tangible tools and resources for current practitioners were also identified in the form of existing training, networking, funding, and career mobility opportunities.
- **Engagement of Wider Stakeholders:** The Sustainability Plan recognizes that there are many different stakeholders involved in the RM Roadmap project whose engagement needs to be encouraged and further supported for sustainability of the emerging enhanced RM landscape to become reality. Therefore, this Sustainability Report recognizes these different stakeholders and the different critical roles they will play in the continuity of the project goals beyond the project lifecycle. Connectivity with the wide community of stakeholders as planned for (and implemented) in the Dissemination Strategy for RM Roadmap showed that there is significant interest in and commitment to the goals of ERA Action 17. Given the impact of the dissemination activities , also to be further supported by ongoing access via websites and promotion by the original project partners after the end of the RM Roadmap project, all the deliverables such as policy briefs, the national and consensus co-creation reports and wider project outcomes will continue to be widely 'disseminated' beyond the partners' original audiences to further drive utility of the results after the project ends.
- **Parallel developments enhancing the RM Profession and Impact:** One exciting additional dimension of this Sustainability Report which could not have been foreseen in the Sustainability Plan submitted at M12 was the pace at which the wider RM landscape would have developed with many actors and actions running in parallel to the RM Roadmap Project. Several critical elements of these parallel achievements are

RM Roadmap_ASTP WP6 D6.2 Sustainability Report

available and referred to as essential ingredients for the Sustainability Report. This updated reality from across the landscape also reinforces the messages that all the stakeholders identified in the RM Roadmap project have continued to identify and accelerate delivery of opportunities directly relevant to the overarching goals of the original RM Roadmap project and ERA Action 17. The RM Competence Framework and other initiatives such as the RM Framework project carry forward the learnings and recommendations of the original goals of the RM Roadmap Project.

11. Sustainability Recommendations to be further reinforced in the final RM Roadmap

It can be seen that the RM Roadmap project has produced many tangible outputs and activities which will continue after the end of the RM Roadmap Project. The role of the Sustainability Report has been to focus on identifying and describing all such actions and ongoing opportunities where the RM landscape comprising all stakeholders (frontline practitioners, their institutional, national and EU-level policymakers and the wider European society) will continue to drive towards an efficient research management landscape as described in ARE action 17.

The final RM Roadmap however will address a much wider range of recommendations which reflect the measures which the European Union, encompassing all its stakeholders, ought to be planning to implement or deliver to ensure that the four drivers for the ERA will be achieved at both national and European level.

Recognition - measures that continue to promote the recognition of RMA as a profession that is a necessary component of a well-functioning of research and innovation system, building upon the RM Competence Framework.

Upskilling - measures that continue to contribute to developing more and better training opportunities for RMA in Europe, with broader sharing of access to existing trainings as well as a framework within which to deliver and develop new trainings – e.g. via the RM Framework outputs.

Networking - providing ongoing evidence and opportunities around networking being an agreed necessary component of career development for RM staff, with enhanced development of and support not only national and regional networks, but also to enable cross-sectoral exchanges via shared networks and conferences.

Capacity-building - promoting the dissemination and use of all aspects of a structured value proposition description for research management to enable policymakers and organizations to dedicate ongoing investment in well-trained RM resources.

Figure 1: Graphic representation of the Overarching Roadmap

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